

Estimation of Arsenic(V) in Organic Compounds in the Presence of Copper(II), Beryllium(II) and Tin(IV)

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THE general survey of literature shows that the methods available for the estimation of arsenic(V) in organic compounds are tedious and time consuming^{1,2}. Wyatt³ has estimated arsenic(V) in the presence of copper bromometrically using a mixture of thioglycolic acid, ascorbic acid and potassium iodide as a reducing agent. In view of the circuitous nature of the methods mentioned above, it was considered desirable to devise some direct and simple method for the estimation of arsenic(V) in the complexes of metal ions such as copper(II), beryllium(II) and tin(IV) with ligand containing arsenic(V).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Pure analytical grade reagents were used. Iodine solution was standardised with standard sodium thiosulphate solution by using freshly prepared starch solution as an indicator.

A known weight of the complex was dissolved in a mixture of glacial acetic and ethyl alcohol. The reduction was carried out by refluxing with zinc dust for about 20 mins. The solution was cooled, filtered and residual zinc dust was washed with aqueous acetic acid. The resulting solution containing arsenic(III) was estimated iodometrically⁴. However, insoluble compounds (SNO 6 and 7) were dissolved in a mixture of 5-6 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 5 ml of ethyl alcohol. The solution was made just alkaline with 4N sodium hydroxide solution. The reduction was carried out subsequently in the presence of acetic acid with zinc dust.

Complexes of tin(IV) can also be estimated by boiling first with 4N sodium hydroxide solution and subsequently adopting above mentioned procedure for reduction and estimation.

A Bajaj potentiometer D-66001 in conjunction with sensitive spot galvanometer (OSAW) and saturated calomel and platinum electrode assembly was used for potentiometric titration.

Results and Discussion

Literature does not record the use of zinc for reducing arsenic(V) in organic compounds. Most of the metal complexes containing arsenic(V) are soluble in alcohol-acetic acid mixture. These have been reduced by zinc dust when copper and tin are eliminated and arsenic(III) in the solution is

estimated iodometrically⁴. However, organo arsenic said complexes with copper(II) are not soluble under similar conditions and a modified method was used as mentioned in the experimental section. The tin(IV) complexes behave in an interesting manner when they are first dissolved in alkalies and subsequently reduced with zinc dust in the presence of acetic acid solutions. Here tin is not eliminated. It is reduced to tin(II) and is estimated alongwith arsenic(III). Thus coupling of the two procedures leads to the facile estimation of arsenic(V) and tin(IV) in their complexes. The results are given in Table 1. Potentiometric method is also applicable to these titrations and results obtained by this method are also indicated in Table 1.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	Weight taken mg.	Weight found mg.	Percentage error
1.	Dichloro(ethylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) copper(II)	10.4	10.49	0.86
		13.4	13.51	0.82
		10.2	10.14	0.58 ^a
2.	Dichloro(butylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) copper(II)	10.0	9.94	0.60
		11.0	10.92	0.73
		12.2	12.02	0.16 ^a
3.	Diaquobis(butylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) copper(II) perchlorate	11.0	11.05	0.45
		16.2	16.15	0.31
4.	Diaquobis(ethylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) copper(II) perchlorate	13.0	13.05	0.38
		15.0	14.90	0.06
		12.0	12.02	0.16 ^a
5.	Dinitrato(ethylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) copper(II)	13.4	13.50	0.74
		16.2	16.27	0.43
		14.0	13.92	0.55 ^a
6.	<i>o</i> -aminophenylarsonato-copper(II)	10.2	10.29	0.82
		13.0	13.00	0.00
7.	<i>o</i> -nitrophenylarsonato-copper(II)	10.0	9.99	0.10
		13.0	13.02	0.15
8.	Basic beryllium acetate-tris (<i>o</i> -carboxyphenyl- <i>p</i> -tolylarsine oxide)	10.4	10.46	0.19
		12.2	11.19	0.09
9.	Basic beryllium acetate-tris (<i>o</i> -carboxyphenyl-diphenylarsine oxide)	10.2	10.13	0.69
		12.2	12.19	0.08
10.	Tetrachloro(ethylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) tin(IV)	10.0	10.03	0.30
		11.0	11.06	0.55
		10.0	9.91	0.90 ^b
		10.4	10.46	0.19 ^b
11.	Tetrachloro(butylenebis-diphenylarsine oxide) tin(IV)	10.2	10.21	0.09
		10.2	10.58	0.19
		10.0	10.08	0.80
		10.8	10.71	0.07

^a indicate results obtained by potentiometric method.^b indicate results when arsenic(V) and tin(IV) are determined simultaneously.

References

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